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NEURAL NETWORKS AS A TOOL FOR DETECTING DRUG TRAFFICKING ON SOCIAL NETWORKS

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Annotation. *The article examines the current problem of illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and their analogues in the digital environment, with an emphasis on the use of social networks for the purpose of selling prohibited substances under the guise of «emojis» as a code language.*

In the scientific work, the author touches upon the experience of individual countries, where government agencies, through comprehensive monitoring and analysis of big data using artificial intelligence, identify and prevent drug crimes committed on social networks.

The transition of drug crime to the digital plane has led to the active use of social networks and messengers for the hidden sale of illegal substances. Dealers use «emoji» as a conditional code that makes it difficult to identify illegal content. The purpose of this study is to analyze the potential of neural network algorithms in detecting such forms of interaction. The methodological framework includes a comparative legal analysis of foreign experience (USA, UK), a content study of preventive materials and a generalization of official crime statistics. It has been established that the introduction of monitoring systems based on artificial intelligence makes it possible to effectively localize digital drug distribution channels.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, it has been proposed to create a register of emoji designations used, integrate «county lines» - tools into cyberpolice practice, and create interdepartmental analytical units. The recommendations are consistent with the provisions of the Message of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated September 8, 2025, aimed at digital transformation of the state system, increasing transparency and effectiveness in combating drug threats in the online space. The presented solutions have practical value for the formation of a modern model of countering cybercrime.

Based on the results of the author's research, separate directions for the introduction of digital technologies and artificial intelligence into domestic law enforcement activities have been formed.

Keywords: *narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, drug crime, social networks, emojis, artificial intelligence, neural networks, counteraction.*

НЕЙРО ЖЕЛІЛЕР ӘЛЕУМЕТТІК ЖЕЛІЛЕРДЕ ЕСІРТКІ ҚЫЛМЫСТАРЫН АНЫҚТАУ ҚҰРАЛЫ РЕТІНДЕ

ӘБИЛДА ЕРАСЫЛ МЕДЕТБЕКҰЛЫ

Қазақстан Республикасы Бас прокуратурасының жанындағы
Құқық қорғау органдары академиясының магистранты

Аннотация. *Мақалада «эмодзи» түріндегі тыйым салынған заттарды код тілі ретінде өткізу мақсатында әлеуметтік желілерді пайдалануға баса назар аудара отырып, сандық ортадағы есірткі, психотроптық заттар мен олардың аналогтарының заңсыз айналымының қазіргі заманғы проблемасы қарастырылады.*

Ғылыми жұмыста автор мемлекеттік органдар жасанды интеллектті қолдана отырып, үлкен деректерді кешенді мониторингтеу және талдау арқылы әлеуметтік

желілерде жасалатын есірткі қылмыстарын анықтайтын және жолын кесетін жекелеген елдердің тәжірибесін қозғайды.

Есірткі қылмысының цифрлық жазықтыққа ауысуы тыйым салынған заттарды жасырын өткізу үшін әлеуметтік желілер мен мессенджерлерді белсенді пайдалануға әкелді. Дилерлер «эмодзилерді» заңсыз мазмұнды анықтауды қиындататын шартты код ретінде қолданады. Осы зерттеудің мақсаты өзара әрекеттесудің осындай формаларын анықтаудағы нейрондық желі алгоритмдерінің әлеуетін талдау болып табылады. Әдістемелік негізге шетелдік тәжірибені салыстырмалы-құқықтық талдау (АҚШ, Ұлыбритания), профилактикалық материалдарды контент-зерттеу және құқық бұзушылықтардың ресми статистикасын қорыту кіреді. Жасанды интеллект негізінде мониторинг жүйесін енгізу есірткі сатудың цифрлық арналарын тиімді оқшаулауға мүмкіндік беретіні анықталды.

Қазақстан Республикасында пайдаланылатын эмодзи-белгілердің тізілімін қалыптастыру, «county lines» - құралдарды киберполиция практикасына интеграциялау және ведомствоаралық талдау бөлімшелерін құру ұсынылды. Ұсынымдар Қазақстан Республикасы Президентінің 2025 жылғы 8 қыркүйектегі мемлекеттік жүйені цифрлық трансформациялауға, онлайн-кеңістіктегі есірткі қатерлеріне қарсы күрестің ашықтығы мен тиімділігін арттыруға бағытталған Жолдауының ережелерімен келісіледі. Ұсынылған шешімдер киберқылмысқа қарсы іс-қимылдың заманауи моделін қалыптастыру үшін практикалық мәнге ие.

Авторды зерттеу қорытындысы бойынша отандық құқық қорғау қызметіне цифрлық технологияларды, жасанды интеллектті енгізудің жекелеген бағыттары қалыптастырылды.

Түйінді сөздер: есірткі, психотроптық заттар, есірткі қылмысы, әлеуметтік желілер, эмодзилер, жасанды интеллект, нейро желілер, қарсы әрекет.

НЕЙРОСЕТИ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ВЫЯВЛЕНИЯ НЕЗАКОННОГО ОБОРОТА НАРКОТИКОВ В СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СЕТЯХ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается современная проблема незаконного оборота наркотических средств, психотропных веществ и их аналогов в цифровой среде, с акцентом на использование социальных сетей с целью сбыта запрещённых веществ под видом «эмодзи» в качестве кодового языка.

В научном труде автором затронут опыт отдельных стран, где государственные органы посредством комплексного мониторинга и анализа больших данных с применением искусственного интеллекта выявляют и пресекают наркопреступления, совершаемые в социальных сетях.

Переход наркопреступности в цифровую плоскость обусловил активное использование социальных сетей и мессенджеров для скрытого сбыта запрещённых веществ. Дилеры применяют «эмодзи» как условный код, затрудняющий выявление противоправного контента. Целью настоящего исследования является анализ потенциала нейросетевых алгоритмов в обнаружении таких форм взаимодействия. Методологическая основа включает сравнительно-правовой анализ зарубежного опыта (США, Великобритания), контент-исследование профилактических материалов и обобщение официальной статистики правонарушений. Установлено, что внедрение систем мониторинга на базе искусственного интеллекта позволяет эффективно локализовать цифровые каналы наркосбыта.

В Республике Казахстан предложено формирование реестра используемых эмодзи-обозначений, интеграция «county lines» - инструментов в практику киберполиции и создание межведомственных аналитических подразделений. Рекомендации согласуются с положениями Послания Президента Республики Казахстан от 8 сентября 2025 года, направленного на цифровую трансформацию государственной системы, повышение прозрачности и эффективность борьбы с наркоугрозами в онлайн-пространстве. Представленные решения имеют практическую ценность для формирования современной модели противодействия киберпреступности.

По итогам исследования автора сформированы отдельные направления внедрения цифровых технологий, искусственного интеллекта в отечественную правоохранительную деятельность.

***Ключевые слова:** наркотические средства, психотропные вещества, наркопреступность, социальные сети, эмодзи, искусственный интеллект, нейросети, противодействие.*

Introduction

The modern drug situation in the world is characterized by a high dynamic development of internal and external factors influencing the change in the structure of the drug market, as well as the transformation of forms, methods of supply and distribution of prohibited substances.

This problem is appropriately reflected in the Concept of Legal Policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2030, which highlights the importance of preventing offenses related to drug trafficking [1].

In the context of the rapid development of digital technologies, the prevention of illicit drug trafficking in the digital space is becoming one of the urgent tasks. Social media platforms such as Instagram and Twitter have become important platforms for the marketing and sale of illicit drugs [2], reaching millions of users worldwide, and are often used by dealers to sell illicit substances and engage young people through hidden messages, including using emojis as a special symbolic language.

The development of the technological aspect of drug crime, its transition to «cyberspace», the use of cryptocurrencies and the emergence of increasingly complex psychoactive substances requires government agencies to consolidate common efforts. In this context, the analysis of current trends and factors influencing the development of the drug situation is of paramount importance for developing specific measures to counter drug crime.

The development of the transport and logistics potential of the Republic of Kazakhstan, including the geographical location of the country at the intersection of major international drug trafficking, determines its vulnerability to transit narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, their analogues and precursors.

To date, facts related to the production of synthetic drugs in clandestine laboratories, the sale of wild-growing cultivated cannabis, and «pharmacy» drug addiction have been revealed.

Materials and methods

The conducted research is based on comparative legal, systematic and analytical approaches. Data from the Qamqor portal for 2022-2025, regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan («On Informatization», «On digital assets in the Republic of Kazakhstan»), as well as international practices of the DEA (USA) and the British police were used as an empirical base. The methods of content analysis, descriptive statistics, and expert evaluation were used, which allowed us to identify gaps in the regulation of digital communications monitoring.

Results

According to the statistical data of the «Qamqor» information portal (portal of legal statistics and special accounting authorities), from 2022 to 2025, there is a steady upward trend in the number of criminal cases sent to court on the facts of illegal manufacture, processing, acquisition, storage,

transportation for the purpose of sale, shipment or sale of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances or their analogues provided for in article 297 of the Criminal Code.

In 2022, 971 criminal cases of this category were sent to court. In 2023, this figure increased to 1,097 cases, which is an increase of more than 13% compared to the previous year. In 2024, the upward trend continued, with the number of cases sent to court reaching 1,413, which is 28.8% higher than in 2023 and 45.5% higher than in 2022. As of September 2025, 1,190 criminal cases have already been registered and brought to court, indicating a high probability of further growth by the end of the year [3].

These statistics indicate the continuing tension in the sphere of illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, as well as an increase in the effectiveness of detecting and documenting illegal activities by law enforcement agencies. At the same time, such dynamics require an in-depth analysis of the factors contributing to the steady growth of these offenses, as well as an assessment of the effectiveness of preventive and repressive measures taken.

In no way criticizing the accumulated experience, in this work we consider it necessary to pay attention to the issue of «counteraction», which includes not only the fight against offenses, but also provides for preventive, preventive measures.

In the era of globalization and digitalization of processes, the Internet is one of the tools used to commit criminal offenses.

Various social networks, the so-called «messengers», are used by intruders to popularize and spread the level of drug use.

The analysis of domestic regulatory legal acts conducted by the authors of the study (for example, the Laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan «On Informatization» [4], «On digital assets in the Republic of Kazakhstan» [5]) showed that the legal space provides for such categories as «information security», «protection of electronic information resources», which are not They cover the issues of monitoring social networks for the use of encrypted messages, the so-called «emojis», in the context of the sale and distribution of prohibited substances.

Discussion

«Emoji» - is a special graphic language of ideograms and emoticons used in electronic messages and web pages, as well as the pictographs themselves. This graphic language, where combinations of pictures are used instead of words, appeared in Japan and then spread around the world.[6]

In our opinion, in response to the affected threat, prevention should include not only constant monitoring and blocking of suspicious content, but also the introduction of modern technologies, neural networks capable of detecting hidden patterns and deciphering disguised messages.

In this area, we believe it is necessary to pay attention to the foreign experience of countries such as the United States of America and the United Kingdom, where an integrated approach is being practiced that combines prevention programs, educational initiatives, and big data analysis using artificial intelligence.

When monitoring the messages, experts from the Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA) in the United States noticed that drug traffickers used seemingly harmless emojis, which in fact were a kind of «language» for encoding types of drugs, their quantity and quality [7].

This circumstance served as the basis for the systematization of the identified symbols, which was appropriately reflected in the official manual «Emoji Drug Code Decoded» [8], which was released by the DEA in 2021 to inform parents, educators and law enforcement officials, which describes in detail the main emojis and their significance in drug trafficking when using a large flow of digital information.

With the help of practical guidance and the use of emoji code, law enforcement officers more effectively monitor and block sales, identify and stop the spread of dangerous drugs.

For example, during the national «One Pill Can Kill» campaign conducted by the DEA from September 29 to December 14, 2021, 8.4 million counterfeit pills were seized, 42% of which contained a lethal dose of fentanyl [9].

In the UK the police Surrey collected and systematized information about the meaning of the many emojis that include, for example: 🐟 (fish) — cocaine 🍓 (strawberry), 🍒 (cherry), 🍰 (cake), 🍦 (ice cream) — cannabis 👽 (alien) and 🎭 (mask) — MDMA, as well as 🦊 (fist) and a 🚀 (rocket), symbolizing the strength and quality of drugs.

As part of preventive measures, the Surrey County Police has developed recommendations for parents and teachers of educational institutions so that they can timely identify signs of possible involvement of young people in illegal activities [10].

In another case, in 2024, the Cheshire County police in the UK used an artificial intelligence system that includes the analysis of digital communications, such as messages on social networks and instant messengers, as well as facial recognition technology, which helped uncover a criminal group involved in the sale of drugs through the «county lines» system (a multi-layered network of inter-regional distribution in which young people often participate in the role of couriers and distributors).

Thanks to the use of artificial intelligence algorithms capable of deciphering hidden «emoji» codes and analyzing related linguistic data, law enforcement agencies were able to identify and localize participants in criminal activity in a timely manner, identify drug distribution patterns, and collect convincing evidence for successful prosecution [11].

In our opinion, the integration of the above-mentioned neural network technologies into domestic law enforcement activities can significantly improve the processes of monitoring, detecting and suppressing drug crimes on social networks and messengers, including the use of emojis as a code in drug traffickers' messages.

Predictive analysis using modern neural networks is promising, while models based on articles have an organic predictive utility and are not suitable for analyzing textual data [12].

Conclusion

The analysis of statistical data showed a steady growth trend in cases under Article 297 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which indicates the expansion of digital channels of drug trafficking. Foreign experience has confirmed the effectiveness of using artificial intelligence to recognize code emojis and identify criminal networks. The «Emoji Drug Code Decoded» manual (DEA, 2021) has been created in the USA, and programs for automatic analysis of social communications and prevention among young people have been implemented in the UK.

There is still no legal mechanism in Kazakhstan that provides comprehensive monitoring of social networks for illegal content. The integration of neural network solutions into the activities of the cyber police will make it possible to identify hidden patterns and prevent the involvement of young people in drug trafficking. It is proposed to create a national emoji registry, implement «county lines» analytics systems, and form digital criminology units in strict compliance with the principles of personal data protection.

The experience of applying system monitoring of the digital space based on artificial intelligence technologies and big data analysis methods indicates the possibility of considering the issue of introducing similar mechanisms into domestic law enforcement activities, for which we suggest that it is advisable to pay attention to the following areas:

- formation of a national register of symbols and symbols (including emojis) used in the field of drug trafficking, with subsequent communication of information to key social institutions;
- implementation of neural network algorithms for automated analysis of digital communications in order to identify hidden patterns characteristic of illegal activities;
- creation of specialized units within the cyber police with competencies in the field of digital criminology, behavioral analysis on the web and visual recognition.

The integration of these technological and organizational solutions into the national law enforcement system will improve the quality of drug crime prevention, especially among young people who are most vulnerable to the digital environment.

We noted that an important stimulating factor for the introduction of such innovations in Kazakhstan is the message of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which highlights the need

for active use of AI technologies in key areas, including law enforcement, in order to modernize and improve performance in the fight against new challenges such as digital crime and drug trafficking [13]. The proposed measures of the conducted research correspond to the tasks outlined in the Message of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan and are aimed at strengthening national security and law and order.

This article was prepared as part of the study of the discipline «Legal regulation of information Technologies» at the Academy of Law Enforcement Agencies at the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the master's degree in Jurisprudence. The research is based on the integration of knowledge gained during the educational process and is aimed at developing practical and analytical skills in the field of digital law and modern technologies.

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